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I, Jon Rzeznik, hereby submit this original work as part of the requirements for the degree of Master of Science in Information Technology-Online.

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Practical Data-Driven Approaches to Application Layer Security With Respect to Internet
of Things Devices in a Modern American Hospital Setting

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by

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ABSTRACT

People know about threats such as ransomware and data breaches potentially affecting healthcare providers through various articles on the news as well as being aware of the impact that the growing dependency of embedded devices has on our care. Given these two conditions, it's fair to ask: what else is being done to ensure public safety when someone's in with a serious medical condition? Who's ensuring that some entity isn't getting in and remotely changing settings on critical care components that could in turn possibly cause someone to needlessly die?

All of these pose excellent questions that deserve to be answered. Yet, there's no easy solution out there. Very few enterprises, much less health systems, are capable of consistently providing more resources such as labor and tools as needed. While a majority of the nation's 5,000 healthcare systems are technically not-for-profit, budget crunches still nonetheless have an adverse impact on security operations. This adverse impact on security operations often means cyberattacks still persist, and we continue to hear about data breaches in the news. It's clear that something practical needs to be done, but what?

DEDICATION

*To all of my fellow cybersecurity professionals who work tirelessly to keep us all safe and
secure*

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

IoT	Internet of Things	13
IoMT	Internet of Medical Things	13
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things	13
SecOps	Security Operations	17
FDA	Food and Drug Administration	18
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning	19
SOHO	Small Office and Home (Office)	21
DoS	Denial-of-Service	29
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service	29
BLE	Bluetooth Low-Energy	65
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force	35
RFC	Request for Comment	36
SOAR	Security Orchestration and Response	67
SoC	System on a Chip	65
BLE	Bluetooth Low-Energy	65
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act	32

1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

1.1 Cybersecurity's Importance in IT

The importance of information technology as a key supporting element of modern civilization is almost self-evident. It also need not be said that with the rise and ubiquity of information technology comes dynamic and concomitant threats. Threats arise not just from the world around us, but also potentially within a given organization. These threats often don't follow the usual social stereotypes around "hackers" that are often presented culturally. Indeed, one example in June 2023 was a cyberattack on several United States Government agencies that in turn has been attributed to a state-sanctioned Russian group. [Lyn23]

Despite what people may hear via their preferred news sources, it's not just remote systems, commercial products, or "Microsoft" that gets hit. Today, just about everything and anything can be a target, and because nothing really is perfect, everything and everything thus is technically vulnerable at one point or another. There is a reason, after all, why users and organizations are consistently reminded to update and patch their software (and at times, firmware and hardware). It's why "Patch Tuesday" still remains a thing twenty years after Microsoft started pushing continual updates on a monthly basis.

The various strains of ransomware that have made global headlines over the past few years are prime examples. Palo Alto's Unit 42 analysis team has noted in their 2023 report that they "see information about seven new victims posted to dark web leak sites—averaging out to about one publicly posted new extortion target every four hours" [Pal23].

That same report noted that while many of these gangs are opportunistic, there are some methods to the madness, like going after high-profile organizations that are perceived as having deep pockets and might be willing to pay to get their data back, and that many of the dark-web repositories are from organizations who refused to pay the demanded ransoms [Pal23].

What's also notable is that holes can appear everywhere – and not just in the commercial, off-the-shelf software that an enterprise uses. Many organizations have specific customized applications or computing platforms to carry out core functions of their practice. These systems in particular raise their own set of issues due to corporate inertia and a general demand for people to avoid touching critical systems that could stop the business. Often, this is due to specific regulations imposed either by laws or by industry standards. As an excellent and rather pertinent example, healthcare organizations such as hospitals and medical practices fit this category exceedingly well.

Security though at the end of the day isn't just about looking for threats. It's a continual give-and-take that at its core revolves around balances and trade-offs. Balances must continually be struck and re-calibrated to provide adequate security of data while still providing enough flexibility for an organization's essential business workflows to continue. [OS13] Risks must be considered holistically and taking workflows and users into account. And, of course, the business and security landscapes remain dynamic in the wake of the global COVID-19 pandemic and an increasing desire to automate workflows.

1.2 Getting Smart: The Rise of Internet of Things

Trends in technology also have given rise to smaller and often embedded “smart” devices that are managed across a network connection. These small smart devices are part of a growing framework that’s often referred to as the “Internet of Things” (or Internet of Things (IoT)). As small as these devices are, they’ve found big uses in various medical (Internet of Medical Things, Internet of Medical Things (IoMT)) and industrial (Industrial Internet of Things, Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)) settings. As a result, the IoT can be visualized as a large set, with IoMT and IIoT as specialized subsets of IoT.

This new frontier opens up a wide array of possibilities for technological innovation, particularly in areas and contexts that would be difficult or impossible for humans to physically perform. As examples, farmers are leveraging IoT and IIoT devices to produce higher crop yields, reduce water usage, require fewer pesticides and fertilizer, lower food costs, minimize runoff and increase worker safety [KH22].

Likewise, IIoT sensors and controllers can perform automated checks on environmental or physical instances, connect to cloud-based technologies, and act based on a programmed flow based on data coming inbound from a given sensor. A good example would be a camera that scans parts coming off an assembly line for quality and tolerance control, allowing the line to automatically reject any faulty parts.

What sets IoT apart though is that despite how small they often are, they can be designed to perform a myriad of differing functions using only a handful of commands and protocols. Many IoT devices for example don’t use HTTP or traditional IP-based networking; instead using low-power technologies and protocols such as Zigbee, CoAP, Bluetooth Low-Energy, 6LoWPAN, and MQTT to effectively connect beyond the typical

TCP/IP network-based communications.

While a steadily-growing number of businesses turn to rely on IoT devices, healthcare settings are unique because of the wide array of IoT, IIoT, and IoMT devices potentially in play behind-the-scenes not just in our care, but also within our day-to-day lives. How so? Consider three different applications: healthcare, industry, and the home.

1.3 In the Hospital: IoT and Healthcare

Though it may seem obvious to the common observer, it bears remembering that everyone at some point in their lives will need to interact with the healthcare system and receive care. Put another way, it is rare indeed for someone to live a long life in a modern Western society and have never once interacted with a doctor, nurse, or pharmacist for a health issue. Nor are all health issues created equal; some of these are intensely personal matters that the average person would never want anyone else to know. Yet, the rise of IoMT as key factors in the delivery of patient care also *ipso facto* means that everyone is directly affected by the quality and reliability of IoMT devices.

The recent pandemic has also by dint of sheer necessity encouraged adoption of new technologies affecting patient care. Whereas devices have been around for decades to help with patient care, the ability to perform remote monitoring, reduce wait times, and improved collection and analysis of pertinent health data to drive patient outcomes. This market explosion is forecasted to continue, potentially reaching \$190 billion by 2028 [KH22].

As a necessary result from this growing deployment of IoMT, healthcare practices are maintaining troves of confidential data that not just expose most every facet of human lives, but also so do the devices that in turn are necessary for healing and/or saving lives. Much of this data is technically covered under federal and state privacy laws when it's generated in a healthcare setting, but just because there are laws mandating privacy do not necessarily mean that the data is always going to be safe. It is therefore a necessity to rethink how data is secured not just in motion, but also at rest.

Today, connected devices are found throughout a hospital campus and are important elements of patient care. Examples of these devices include, but are by no means limited to:

- insulin pumps
- hand-washing stations
- bedside and heart monitors
- surgical robots
- connected inhalers
- mood-aware trackers for depression and anxiety.

At the same time, healthcare systems are also known for using devices long past their end-of-life date, often due to their function and large replacement costs. Other devices are designed with a long life in mind, such as a 20 year span [Sto21], which necessarily means that at some point, these devices are running on outdated technology that in turn proves vulnerable; it's estimated that sixty percent of these devices are at or past the

end-of-life date set by their vendors [Sto21].

What's also crystal-clear in the security world is that these facts haven't been lost on the seedier elements of the Internet. Cybercriminals know of these developments, and it's no wonder why the healthcare sector is considered to be a continually rich and tempting global target. This trend is also one that is painfully well-known among healthcare security teams. Within recent memory, there already have been incidents where hospitals have been forced to close their doors as a result of cyber-related attacks, further straining the communities in which they've served. In one particularly horrible case, people in rural LaSalle County, Illinois now must travel over 30 minutes for emergency-room and obstetrics services due to the ransomware-related closure of St. Margaret's Hospital [Col23]

Despite this rising threat though, investments in security are often hard to justify. Healthcare systems also have limited income, and there are also more pressing challenges two years after the ravages of the COVID-19 pandemic. Most notably, the pandemic has exacerbated a staffing drain due to burnout, and much of what's coming in is often geared on recruiting and retaining clinical staff despite severe shortages that are increasingly visible to patients. While the merits, sources, and economic effects of these staffing issues are still being debated, more than half of America's 5,000 hospitals are technically non-profit organizations [RTSG22]. This is in contrast to a perception that hospitals are necessarily for-profit companies looking to wring out every possible dollar from patients and employees.

Naturally, this means that there's fewer dollars and less resources that can be spread around the non-clinical and non-staffing departments to work with, and this includes

information security. This is going on despite the growth of devices and the concomitant data that's being generated as a result of patient care. Major expenditures or mass-replacement of systems are thus likely to not be approved without executive buy-in, mandates from regulators, and/or an exceedingly-compelling business case.

Yet, failures in information security can have a deleterious impact on the clinical care of a patient. Integrated systems in modern patient care mean that a misstep or security breach can quickly escalate into life-or-death situations that pose what would otherwise be considered unacceptable risks for a patient. This was very unfortunately illustrated in September 2020 when a ransomware attack at the Düsseldorf University Hospital left 30 of its servers in a crippled state and forced redirects of critical-care patients, one of whom died as a result of the delay. While this may have been an indirect cause and perhaps the first to gain widespread notice, it most certainly won't be the last.

Given these tools, there's an effective system in place, but yet there's always this gut-sense notion that somehow, things are still falling through the cracks. It is not difficult to put an ear out on various web fora such as Reddit and hear about the growing concerns regarding sensors, namely that these sensors are often putting out unwanted noise to Security Operations (SecOps) teams while at the same time legitimate issues somehow end up being overlooked. This is particularly true given results of recent penetration tests and "red team / blue team" exercises where the red team "attacker" was often able to abuse older devices as well as network infrastructure.

Often, documentation and resources on hand are also challenges. One major concern is that information is found to be "tribal knowledge" that is easily at risk of disappearing. Other times, such documentation is missing or wholly inaccurate. This has been

particularly true in the author's experience within the current ambit of his employment, where there are thousands of smaller network-connected biomedical and other embedded devices. Many of these devices are notoriously difficult to track down; the current strategy has been largely to see if these devices show up on stock vulnerability scans and if they contain obvious vulnerabilities (such as default credentials or known defective versions of software).

One thing that needs emphasis is that this sort of situation isn't always the fault of the hospital system. Rather, it's the natural result of numerous factors involving vendors, certification, and even bureaucratic "red tape" in the government. As a pertinent example, many IoMT and IIoT devices are developed with a specific operating system version and specific versions of software installed.

This is especially true in healthcare, where many IoMT devices are built at that specified level and are then given certification from the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) certification. FDA certification is necessary for these devices to legally be used for patient care in the United States. Often as a direct result of costs, many vendors don't always upgrade or update the components as there's fear that doing so triggers a not-insignificant cost to them just to re-submit patches and updates back to the FDA for re-certification.

With over 5000 different healthcare systems in America and over half being non-profits meant for care [RTSG22], there's a lot of coverage and myriads of varying devices out there. On top of this, there are staffing concerns that in turn put further strains on patient care; connected devices that can do some of the monitoring is seen as a godsend to decimated clinical teams. While there is some argument over who and/or what is blame regarding the staffing crisis, it is enough for now to simply say that major budgetary cuts

around hospital systems nationwide are having deleterious impacts on care. Indeed, one system's use of robots even got the he New York Times, noting that "aides would be replaced by AvaSure's 'TeleSitters.' By 2019, Ascension had installed 450 of the robots in more than 50 of its hospitals. The devices – essentially a video camera mounted on a metal pole – send live footage to an off-site command center, where workers talk to patients through speakers in the machine" [RTSG22].

For their parts, the doctors on staff that are looking at the potential equipment being purchased are naturally more concerned about efficacy in terms of the clinical setting and management is concerned about costs. Neither group, from what is known, tends to put cybersecurity risk of the devices as a front-and-center concern, instead noting that this is ostensibly what the IT security teams are for. Not surprisingly, this has the end result of "pointing fingers" if and when a related breach does occur.

1.4 It's Also in the (Industrial) Control Room

Similarly, issues in related IIoT controls often appear; IIoT being seen often in the building management, heating/ventilation/air-conditioning Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC), and physical security systems. They can potentially provide ingress into an enterprise network, as the 2013 Target breach showed. In that incident, attackers stole third-party credentials from an HVAC vendor and were able to laterally move into the Target store chain's enterprise network to exfiltrate approximately 40 million credit card numbers and personal data on as many as 70 million people [HS22].

While it is true that hospitals do use IIoT, they're also used in other environments as well and often have similar issues. Industrial controls, for example, aren't just used in

manufacturing or factory floors; they're also found in commercial building and environmental control units. It need not be said that if these devices are misconfigured or somehow left for open access, these open IIoT devices can provide an easy ingress into a corporate network.

The Target breach also put the spotlight on what has more recently been characterized as a supply-chain attack; the ultimate cause was that the attackers gained access to Target's HVAC vendor by an email phishing campaign, and from there were able to obtain the necessary credentials to not only gain access to Target's HVAC systems, but then exploit the web app to pivot around, daisy-chain various attack methods, and compromise their Active Directory infrastructure by giving themselves domain-admin credentials. [Ola14]. The end result? The attackers were able to pilfer the card and PII data through Target's HVAC vendor.

In short, IIoT and related components can be found to manage everything from the time clocks and security fobs to the building's heating, plumbing, and air conditioning. While these aren't necessarily things that easily come to mind when the topic of IoT devices is brought up, they do in fact count and are vital parts of operating the physical premises.

1.5 A New Approach: Thinking Outside the Box

At the same time, it's also difficult for a security team to vet a new device coming into a hospital – whether it's biomedical, building control, or even a generic door lock. Obtaining actual devices and setting up a test environment is rarely practical, often risks bordering on the unethical usage of data and technology, and in most cases an outright

cost-prohibitive option. So what's a security engineer to do?

It is interesting that there's another class of IoT devices that often follow similar design strategies, and in many cases have similar flaws. These devices are commercially available off-the-shelf and today are relatively inexpensive. Such devices of course are in turn designed for homes and smaller/branch office deployments.

There are difference though in that home devices are typically designed for simple and flat networks whereas enterprise-grade devices often sit on network segments such as virtual local area networks (VLANs). VLANs though often are relatively flat for that segment, so there necessarily isn't any major difference aside from network devices themselves. Also of note is that family and generational dynamics can play an outsized role. For example, it's a generally observable fact that younger generations tend to be more adept and comfortable with emerging technologies. When these family dynamics are factored in, there exist non-zero adverse risks to the home network that might not have been thought of before.

Ultimately, there is one thing that can be done: refine the methods by which devices are evaluated and wherever possible, mitigated by patches or by appropriate security controls. This would be true regardless if the devices in question are a basic forty dollar camera from the local electronics shop or a two million dollar surgical robot.

Thus, it is also worth considering home devices in analysis. Small Office and Home Office (Small Office and Home (Office) (SOHO)) networks and devices often don't get a lot of attention, particularly from a security perspective, until something major happens. This is particularly true with the influx of Internet of Things (IoT) devices that are designed with

the intent to be used in a home in a way that usually foregoes customized setup options to operate and use. Yet at the same time, these devices can potentially provide unintentional ingress in ways that can pose security risks to users on these home and small office networks.

SOHO environments by their very nature often run on several key assumptions that in turn affect how security really plays out on such a network. One of these key assumptions is the fact that SOHO devices are out being sold to the general public and often in everyday stores at very affordable price points. Indeed, many IoT and other network devices point to the apparent ease of setup and use right on the boxes.

Oftentimes, it's clear that many of the people purchasing these devices do not necessarily have technical prowess or familiarity with IoT and security practices. Consequently, it is entirely possible that devices could be set up with weak or non-existent security controls by users who through no inherent fault of their own. Such is often the case already with respect to wireless credentials; according to a 2020 report done by Proofpoint, only 49% of adults surveyed password-protect their wireless networks, 31% have changed the default password on their router, and only 19% have checked or updated their router's firmware. [Pro20].

Thus, the question of just "how secure" are many of these home devices is one that is worth exploring and figuring out. The security of these devices in turn carries a roughly inverse relationship in that the weaker the security on board the device, the easier it ultimately is for a casual attacker to break in. To be sure, just about anything can be compromised with sufficient time and resources. Rather, the focus here is to look for the metaphorical "low-hanging fruit" that unsophisticated attackers might be able to use for

their own benefit.

At the same time, when such devices are found by concerned individuals-be it a homeowner or someone on an enterprise SecOps team, the big questions always seem to boil down to: “what do we do about it?” and more precisely “how can we secure it even if we don’t have admin/root access to install our sensors and other security software safely without jeopardizing function, key workflows, or possibly even government or regulatory approval?”

1.6 Defining the Problem

It is clear that staffing implications resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic have resulted in accelerating the rise of IoT adoption in healthcare. Despite this acceleration trend, there remain risks associated with legacy applications and outdated systems that even the boldest institutions have decreasing appetite for. At the same time, newer solutions and technologies (such as virtualization) are arriving that can potentially enable bridging and utilization of newer systems and applications that in turn offer greater security coverage.

Even though this technology may be available to healthcare systems and might well be used going forward, it still doesn’t address the here-and-now issue that security teams are facing: with limited resources available in terms of financial, technical, time, and manpower, how can a security engineer start looking for loose ends to plug up? This very question is the key question facing healthcare security engineers when faced with system IoT equipment?

While there has been research and tools available, there is a further issue in that research and praxis may be done on a corporate level and thus only available to “big players” who

can afford large sums of money for new technologies and processes. The case study here establishes though that such research and innovation, and the fruits thereof, necessarily needs to be accessible to even the smallest players such as local offices.

2 REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

2.1 Internet of Things Security as a General Concept

Given the rise of IoT devices, it is no surprise that ongoing research and innovation into IoT continues onward to the present and will continue going forward. As more use cases develop and IoT devices continue pushing forward into our technical mainstream simultaneously to the dynamic cybersecurity landscape, the necessity of stronger IoT security continues to become readily apparent.

This rise in IoT has simultaneously presented varying challenges that have been noted over the years, and not just within the ambit of technical journals or even within the security community. One clear example was back in 2016, when John Daley noted that three different factors are in play that together shine a light:

- Of the billions of IoT devices out there, most are somehow connected to the Internet as we know it
- The very fractured nature of the software development industry, particularly with regards to legal and economic structures, leaves no single entity with enough incentives to properly secure their offering
- Closed-source development often means that security vulnerabilities are often impossible to patch

[Dal16]

But this is only scratching the surface with respect to IoT devices in general. Consider that there's the wide array of potential development, the growing methods with which devices can be attacked, and the spread of recent malware attacks against IoT such as Mirai and

Emotet. Clearly, this is quite a bit to unpack. Wazid et al. in 2019 did quite a thorough analysis on some of the security challenges facing IoT. In particular, they weighed the benefits of IoT against its challenges and found that "IoT/IoMT based applications facilitate our everyday life. However, there is also a dark side of this, because it suffers from various security and privacy issues. We have noticed that malware attacks launched by Mirai, Reaper, Echobot, Emotet, Gamut and Necurs botnets are active these days" [WDR⁺19]

2.2 With More Applicability to IoMT Devices

There are a lot of generic and higher-level papers that play into security, the application layer, or biomedical devices. However, there is still a relative dearth on application-layer security with IoT and/or IoMT and specifically geared towards potential real-world praxis of academic cybersecurity research. This dearth exists despite an acknowledged situation where IoMT is expected to be "the future of current healthcare systems where every medical device will be connected and monitored over the Internet via healthcare professionals" [RS22]

Rather, much of the existing literature has focused on cyber risk and impact of cyberattacks on hospitals in terms of theoretical ideas, academic research surveys, or mild investigations into certain events into the matter. On a similar level, the state of the research into the application layer for IoT, IIoT, and IoMT has been looked at extensively, but also on much more of a high-level meta-survey overview. None seem to be able to provide a substantive lesson for someone actively in the field to be able to work to apply these ideas.

In short, the existing literature suggests that while this is a topic worthy of study, nobody has really seemed to push the research or investigate how it could be applied in a real-world or “industry” setting. This is the key factor: it is simply not enough to figure out an effective method; it is also important to be able to apply it. Theory must necessarily follow into praxis.

There have been both discussion of extending current cybersecurity praxis into the IoMT realm as well as the possibility of emerging technologies

Some of the research that has been done up to this point that might provide promise include using Incremental Naïve Bayes and Hoeffding Trees as part of a lightweight early attack detection system for IoMT devices that operate in a “fog” setting [HSAL⁺21] and employing Granular Computing techniques [KPCP19] with respect to network anomaly detection. It is clear that both of these ideas show promise, but again, there’s the question of praxis, in particular: “how can this be developed into something useful out in the field?”

In particular, consider the conference paper written by Kozik, et al. mentioned above. This is about practical employment of granular computing by partitioning data into information granules and then using those granules as “tiny parts of a larger construct, which describe a particular facet of that construct when viewed from a particular level of granulation”. [KPCP19]. Yet the authors also note that to the best of their knowledge, “granular computing has not yet been widely examined nor sic adapted for cybersecurity application purposes.” This of course raises fair questions about availability and practicality within the context of a real-world security team.

The common thread in so many of these papers is this: we have ideas that might very well be effective in areas such as intrusion detection and prevention, securing protocols, and

protecting older devices that may not be up to date (for example, by having outdated systems, tools, or technologies). We can forecast how these technologies can be used to improve patient care and fuse in such ways to enable remote diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment without specifically requiring proximity in physical location. We can set requirements of a secure environment and justify these requirements because "several factors contribute to IoMT devices being vulnerable due to poor design and unregulated or ineffectively regulated environments. These vulnerabilities leave the devices exposed and susceptible to threats so that attackers can gain access to them and to the network infrastructure to which they are connected" [MG22]. Yet we still really don't know how this would play out right now in an actual healthcare system's information security software and processes.

This is true of the papers and especially of the 2021 book

Do No Harm: Protecting Connected Medical Devices, Healthcare, and Data From Hackers and Adversarial Nation States by Matthew Webster. Arguably, this is the most complete investigation specifically addressing the security of medical devices. It's also geared a bit more towards leadership positions that in turn have a clear stake in the issues and ramifications of device security. As such, Webster's book mentions several strong approaches hospital systems could take, such as:

- Factor in cybersecurity in system-wide strategic sourcing, for example, looking for UL 2900 compliance (p. 332)
- Implement compliance modeling with current standards like the NIST Cybersecurity Framework and SOC 2 Type 2 (pp. 333-334)
- Ensuring adequate investment in a multi-prong approach to cybersecurity (p. 341)
- Knowledge of, and appropriate alignment toward, risk appetites (p. 345)

These items are still important not just to IoMT, but also to other categories of IoT as many of the same issues and ideas mentioned are just as applicable. At the same time though, it's worth noting that many healthcare systems unfortunately don't do this, and as a result, breaches and other cybersecurity disasters happen.

One need only to look at various healthcare breaches that have happened since late 2020, and it's a fair bet to say that while some hospitals are still using flat or wide-open networks, others aren't [Web21, p.47]. Along these same lines, it's also reasonable to figure that most systems are at least nominally paying heed to the various HIPAA (and, where applicable, state) regulations. Even so, there are problems that have arisen. As mentioned in the intro, Stockdale (2021) notes that sixty percent of medical devices have reached the end of life. When medical imaging devices alone are considered, seventy percent are on operating systems that have limited or no further support from the vendor on account of age [Web21, p.6]

These realizations make perfect sense when the types of attacks that tend to happen the most are considered. According to Webster, "the most common forms of attack utilizing internet-connected medical devices are ransomware and distributed denial of service attacks" [Web21, p.4]. The trends have become so well-known that articles about major ransomware, generic denial-of-service (Denial-of-Service (DoS) and distributed denial-of-service (Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS)) attacks start to consistently reach mainstream news media outlets. Clearly then, there exists some sort of cybersecurity pandemic.

Sadly, ransomware-related attacks on healthcare systems have ended up costing innocent lives. On September 10, 2020, attackers hit 30 different servers at the Düsseldorf

University Hospital, albeit in an attempt to hit a different university. A patient needed immediate care and as a result of systems being down, experienced a delay in treatment which resulted in the patient's death. [Web21, p.5]. Even when lives aren't directly rendered at stake, the costs to systems can be devastating, as hospitals focus on human life even at costs to its own security [Web21, p.326].

Despite this incident, investments in IoT go on, and the pace of healthcare IoMT adoption continues towards an overarching goal of becoming "smart hospitals." Ranganyaki, et al. (2021) noted in their case study four specific goals of a smart hospital:

- Network Connectivity
- Proper Optimization
- Improved doctor/staff - patient communication
- Appropriate Cybersecurity Settings,

[RSG⁺21]

As smart hospitals per Ranganyaki would imply the effective usage of IoMT devices, it is possible to consider other factors about these devices, such as that IoMT devices must be FDA-approved, including for changes and that FDA approval can take as long as 5 to 6 years [Web21, p.37].

At the same time, there's often not a lot of information that's readily available about these devices. On top of this, there are other research articles and information that is definitively corporate in nature, and thus slanted towards sales of a particular company's product. Such literature is by its very nature biased with the goal of making a sale to a particular

system, so shortcomings aren't going to appear at all.

There are legitimate reasons for this situation, such as:

- With IoT devices in particular, there is a bit of confusion with respect to the term “application layer”
 - The traditional OSI model would strictly delineate the application layer at the top-most official layer, which is layer 7.
 - IoT and IoMT tend to combine these similarly to the existing TCP/IP model
- Healthcare is an example of a heavily regulated industry
 - Thus, regulation by state and federal actors may possibly restrict or prohibit disclosure of certain aspects of a security plan
- Reports are often done by think-tanks, the federal HHS, or state regulators on security matters
- Other research either focuses on healthcare devices generally or focuses on applications/platforms on a broader level
- Many vendors do research for their clients, but it's framed far more as to how that vendor's solutions meet client problems; there are thus questions of bias involved

When we consider each of the research questions, it is quite clear that these reasons outline why there isn't a lot of direct research that is available, but it doesn't also rule out that such research may also run into the “file drawer” problem where potential research may have already been done but is sitting away in a proverbial file cabinet. As there is currently no way to prove or disprove the existence of such research, it is entirely

plausible that research on the topic exists but is inaccessible.

2.2.1 IoMT Ethics

For reasons that are practically self-evident, ethical behaviors and actions are an absolute necessity in healthcare. After all, healthcare is in many respects the ultimate life-or-death situation as well as a groundswell of intimately-tied data that completely reveals the entirety of a person from multiple axes such as physical, mental, emotional, and lifestyle health. With these emphases as ongoing concerns, there is a growing wealth of research into IoMT devices and the ethical considerations that necessarily arise.

Ethical concerns are also one of the key drivers of existing federal and state regulations, most notably the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) of 1996 and California's Confidentiality of Medical Information Act. In such laws, and the related agency regulations deriving from these laws, there are specific definitions of who is covered and which data is legally protected. Hospital systems are almost always covered, and protected health information is broadly defined. Often, such data includes anything that could conceivably "fingerprint" or positively identify a particular patient.

Given this definition, and the fact that IoMT devices tend to interact with copious amounts of data, this means that the processes governing data collection and protecting such data against any unauthorized disclosures are themselves key factors tied to IoMT. In a systematic review published in 2022 and available through the National Institute of Health, Zakerabasali et al. performed a systematic review, and within the data-collection analysis noted: "For example, violation of individuals' privacy is one of these challenges. Most people's information may be used for various purposes without their awareness of

individuals” [ZA22]. This is pertinent given that collections of IoMT sensors are capable of generating large amounts of medically-relevant data that by its very nature carries sensitive information and must be secured against both intentional and unintentional disclosure. Yet, as Zakerabasali notes, it’s also not just about the data in motion that can plague IoMT devices; data at rest in the cloud must also be secured according to the well-known CIA triad, with an emphasis on four major axes of data security:

- Encryption using current SSL/TLS methods
- Server-Side Security against exploits and vulnerabilities on the server applications and infrastructure
- Client-Side Security for the end-user application to access the service
- Password Security - ”care should be given when choosing a password”

[ZA22]

This is also a salient point that Osei-Bonsu et al. noted back in 2018. In particular, their paper noted not just threats that ”include breach of data privacy and other adversarial threats like stealing or destroying information, causing personal injury, and in some cases digital extortion” but also that many devices are made ”available through legal distribution channels that exclude them from existing data privacy and cybersecurity regulations.”

[OBSB18]

Thus, it can be said that there’s a common theme emergent in that these ethical questions of security and privacy are not only continuing to be asked, but they are going deeper into the personal ramifications of the data and usage of these devices. In addition, such ethical questions are still neither going away nor finding satisfactory answers that provide for a clearly-satisfactory continuing resolution. The argument therefore stands that research into

IoMT must consider and, if possible, include the ethical ramifications of IoMT data and usage. Moreover, the current state of affairs strongly suggests that ethical questions and considerations with regards to cybersecurity need to be passed down from academia into industry as research and innovation continue to work through from research into praxis.

2.3 With Specific Respect to Home Devices

2.3.1 General Notes

Over the last few years, more attention has been driven towards the security of home devices, particularly with respect to embedded firmware. Romana et al. detailed a generic process for analyzing the firmware of SOHO Wi-Fi routers for vulnerabilities and provided a case study using a Netis WF2411 router [RGE20]. While this was published back in 2020, it is definitely worth noting that IoT uptake has increased over the past three years, and especially if the global effects of the COVID-19 pandemic are considered.

There have also arisen cases where sophisticated threat actors, including potential groups tied to state-sponsored activity are using SOHO routers and other devices as stealthier initial compromise points [Per22]. In one notable example from 2022, a particular nasty named ZuoRAT worked by using a MIPS file to perform simple enumeration and provide a list of potential targets for HTTP and DNS hijacking; it appears this closely resembled the infamous Mirai botnet malware that crippled Internet systems back in 2017 [Goo22]

While there are a lot of different protocols involved with home devices, one of the more common ones is Zigbee as it works well with home automation. Radhanand et al. in 2021 outlined the practicality of using Zigbee as part of an immune home automation network, noting that it worked but Zigbee's "messaging format sic currently used is rudimentary

and is not suitable for adding more nodes” but the authors go on to say that as ”the network size increases, data from a node might not reach the central node in a single hop.” [RKNSR21]

Zigbee is one of many protocols used in smart home devices largely as a result of no single unifying standard for home IoT being developed until late 2022. This is clear in the marketplace when a single store will sell devices compatible with Google, Amazon Alexa, Apple HomeKit, TP-Link Kasa, Samsung SmartThings, and many other platforms. This has been noted recently as Zegeye et. al observed in January 2023: ”IoT devices from different vendors and protocols don’t work with each other. Each IoT protocol needs a separate hub and app to control it. This is due to multiple propriety systems in the market today.” [ZJK23]

In the same proceedings paper by Zegeye et al, the authors outlined the issue with glaring specificity and made the argument for a unifying home IoT standard, noting that home IoT adoption in the United States is struggling ”due to the need for a robust interoperability ecosystem. The ecosystem is fragmented, which presents difficulties for inter-device communications from different vendors.” The authors continue to note that while Thread is an open standard, consumer devices based specifically on it are not yet available, though many devices are noted as being compatible. However, this is likely to change, as ”Thread is specifically designed for Home Automation and thus supports a wide variety of home use applications including, appliances, access control, climate control, energy management, lighting, safety, and security.” [ZJK23]

Zegeye et al. also raise an excellent point, noting the ability of Thread to naturally utilize various protocols based on established standards such as the Internet Engineering Task

Force (IETF)'s Request for Comment (RFC). These RFCs can be adopted as Internet Standards that allow for vendor-agnostic interoperability. As an example, the Internet Protocol suite is considered an Internet Standard where technical adherence is required for interoperability (and thus conformity with the standard) without regard to the device or vendor being used.

3 METHODS

3.1 Determining A Way Forward

3.1.1 Designing An Environment to Scale

In determining a methodology that would be appropriate to scale, it's worth remembering from the introduction that obtaining actual IoMT devices for the purposes of setting up a test environment to go through security issues is generally impractical and not likely to happen. Likewise, full-on audits of production devices are often impractical due to these devices being used in patient care and thus presenting serious ethical and legal considerations.

Because of these concerns related to medical and industrial devices, alternate means of being able to analyze IoT devices were considered. Of these, the most practical and feasible way was to set up a network with various devices that might be similar of what may be in play in a hospital room. These include varied environmental sensors, automation controls, building controllers, audio/video communications, and cameras.

It is indeed worth noting that design characteristics of devices remain rather consistent; fundamentally, the hardware internals of a given device are quite similar and given human nature, software designs and potential vulnerabilities aren't necessarily far apart. Put another way, manufacturers and designers of IoT devices gravitate towards certain designs in both their hardware (such as chip packages and architecture) and software (such as the firmware's system base), which in turn can impact the vulnerability of these devices.

3.1.2 Considering and Applying Ethics

IoT devices are often used in various contexts involving personal data, particularly with respect to those found in homes and healthcare settings. Such devices often detect and transmit data that in turn can yield confidential or sensitive information that under current laws and regulations may be required to be protected against unauthorized usage and disclosure.

With IoMT, connected devices are often used in the course of patient care and can reveal not just diagnoses, but efficacy of treatment and other patient-vital information. Analyzing the data into such devices would almost invariably end up running into issues regarding the research turning into human experimentation and the necessities of obtaining informed consent as well as institutional review board (IRB) approval in order to remain ethical.

In a home, such considerations are still important but far less clear than a medical practice. Consider the availability of two-way devices such as smart cameras and baby/pet monitors. Many (if not most) do in fact enable remote communication and are bought by consumers for exactly that purpose. However, these devices are ostensibly designed to be used responsibly; the typical use-cases for which such devices are marketed are in "public" rooms of a house such as a kitchen or living room.

While such devices can be used unethically (such as being hidden in a bathroom or bedroom to tap into intimate moments or otherwise "spy" on people without their knowledge and consent), the generally-understood placement for home devices tend to be either outside the home, which is generally open to the public, or within living spaces that are potentially-visible to passers-by and visitors anyway (such as a front living room or den). Nevertheless, different people do have differing feelings with respect to privacy and

determining how much exposure is too much.

3.2 Improvising Without Access to Medical Devices

3.2.1 Setting Up An Environment – The Methods

Even though actual medical devices and a regular hospital room (or, for that matter, medical exam room) were not available, this didn't necessarily mean that research must come to an end on account of availability. As mentioned above, IoT devices between purposes do share quite a few similarities and pitfalls, which means that it is at least theoretically feasible to model the base security of such devices (and the potential means of sniffing out the basic issues) in a different setting. Enter the home.

A working lab environment was set up in the author's home using smart home devices of varying functions and categories with the goal to be at least reasonably representative in terms of generic class or function. In this way, these representative IoT devices were able to be used as intended, but also to hone ways that can scale up or down to extend the practical effect of this research. The specific setup of being in a home where there exists a need to consider privacy considerations also clearly affords a view into protocols and data transportation.

The existing wireless network infrastructure was converted over and given a Class B private network address of 172.20.10.0/24. This connected on the regular home network with a static IP of 10.10.10.2 and static routing configured in the home router to ensure ingress and egress to the Internet. The TP-Link router was secured with WPA2 and followed with setup instructions, which disallowed default credential usage. A reference

topology is included in the Appendix.

Three different devices have potential bridging and/or hub functionalities, which in turn provided the ability to observe and interact with the IoT devices within the network. These were the HomePod Mini, which served as the HomeKit "master" node and controlled the home environment, one Athom HomeyBridge with inbuilt Zigbee support, and a Raspberry Pi (RPi) 4B configured with the latest HomeBridge combined image flashed onto a standard 32GB micro-SD card.

In addition to the IoT devices themselves, two virtual machines (VMs) were installed. One was set up for monitoring the network (e.g. with the Nordic dongle), and the other was configured with a standard "large" install of Kali Linux to represent our "attacker" on the local network. Both of these machines were configured with bridged networking over to the wireless network. These two are important machines to consider as IoT devices on a SOHO network often aren't segregated from everyone else. Accordingly, our "monitoring" VM can represent a generic PC and our "attacker" is plausibly represented by the presence of a Kali VM on the local network.

As the Windows virtual machine sat on a 2015 iMac running VMware Fusion 13, this physical machine was by pure necessity connected to the local network and used as a "neutral" machine recording raw Wireshark packet-capture data off of the wireless interface. It also served as the physical device carrying the USB ports for the Nordic Semi 802.15.4 dongle attached to Windows as well as a 5TB external drive for data collection.

The IoT devices chosen are contained in the below two tables; the first being those devices visible on the local wireless LAN, and the second counting devices that are using IoT

transports such as CoAP, Zigbee, and Thread:

Model	Vendor	Price	Device Type	Network address
Archer A20	TP-Link	\$160	Wireless Router	172.20.10.1
Homey Bridge	Athom	\$70	Smart Bridge	172.20.10.22
Kasa EP40a Outdoor Plug	TP-Link	\$20	Outdoor Plug	172.20.10.40
32" Roku TV	Philips	\$120	Smart TV	172.20.10.48
RPi HomeBridge	RPi	\$150	Smart Bridge	172.20.10.67
C253 myQ Door Opener	Chamberlain	N/A	Garage Door Opener	172.20.10.104
Samsung 7 Series TV	Samsung	N/A	Smart TV	172.20.10.128
HomePod Mini	Apple	\$100	Smart Hub/Speaker	172.20.10.152
Circle View Camera	Logitech	\$150	Smart Camera	172.20.10.157
Eufy Security Camera	Anker	\$40	Smart Camera	172.20.10.220
Arlo Spotlight Camera	Arlo	\$70	Smart Camera	172.20.10.230
Nanoleaf A19 47FH	Nanoleaf	\$20	Smart Lightbulb	fd9c Unique-Local
Nanoleaf A19 063S	Nanoleaf	\$20	Smart Lightbulb	fd9c Unique-Local
Eve Energy Plug	Eve (ABB)	\$40	Indoor Smart Plug	fd9c Unique-Local
Trådfri Outlet (E1706)	IKEA	\$22	Indoor Smart Plug	0x000d6ffffe7cebd6
Trådfri Switch (E1703)	IKEA	\$0	Outlet Switch	0x000d6ffffeaf800f
Wemo WSP100 SmartPlug	Belkin	\$25	Indoor Smart Plug	fd9c Unique-Local

Table 3.1 continued from previous page

Table 3.1: Full List of IoT Devices

This can be visualized as a network topology, as demonstrated below:

Figure 3.1: Network Topology

Measurement of the results were also considered, with the realization that a full compromise was not necessary to impair or disrupt the basic designed functions of the device. Accordingly, a scale was devised to consider how severe the impact might be and was defined as follows:

- Not Compromised: the attacker fails to gain meaningful access to the device's data and communications and the device continues to function as intended

- Partially Compromised: the attacker manages to gain a foothold into the device's underlying system, but cannot go further to disrupt or destroy service
- Functionally Compromised: the attacker does any of the following:
 - puts the device out of service (such as via a denial-of-service attack
 - manages to bypass or subvert key device functions,
 - successfully intercepts, manipulates, or forges communications emanating from or directed to the device
 - * if communications are encrypted, the attacker must decrypt the communications successfully
 - changes configured credentials at will without administrative or "root" level access
- Fully Compromised: the attacker can gain access and fully commandeer the device for their own ends; they can change any characteristic at will and even install persistence to maintain access

Before the scans began, the scope and complexity of the hypothetical attacker needed to be considered. As this was a home-network scenario, a baseline of unsophisticated users and attackers was considered and adopted. Ultimately, this was decided on the grounds of practicality and being able to create enough of a demonstration within the bounds of what people and manufactures might be familiar with as well as keeping to a realistic scenario. At the same time, items such as attacker skill and location are also variables and thus the idea would be to generate something that might be applicable in a higher-level situation.

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In the scenario covered here, seven basic assumptions were made:

- The devices were set up by the owners (e.g. the adults in the house), with the full knowledge of what they do, to achieve a specific lawful and ethical goal (for example, monitoring the dog and baby when away or ensuring that the kids and/or grandkids don't go throughout the house)
- The owners setting the devices up are able to follow the basic directions/guides/wizards that come with the device or through a smartphone app, but don't know much more about networks, security or IoT; they could very well be parents or grandparents
- The person(s) in the attacker role carry sustained physical access to the devices and the local network
- The attacker has basic technical knowledge and a bit of security familiarity but isn't also a professional pentester or skilled hacker
 - The attacker knows how to install Kali Linux on a laptop and try poking around with the included tools but not much more than that
- There are some defensive tools active on the underlying network
 - It is thus possible to surveil and detect any sort of activity on the network – be it offensive or defensive
- There are other people around at varying times during the day who also use services on the network
- These users aren't necessarily technical but also can suspect if there's something amiss

After determining the devices and what function they provide to the home, the initial step was to configure them. For the purposes of testing, setup instructions were followed, and

default credentials were left as-is in order to best approximate a situation where a consumer buys and sets up these devices without necessarily understanding security practices or cyber hygiene. While this does raise some questions about the propriety of such an exercise, it is worth noting that according to ProofPoint's 2020 User Risk Report, only 31 percent of respondents have changed the default password on their router, and only 45 percent have personalized their wireless network name [Pro20]. This strongly suggests that many, if not most, people tend to set-and-forget their tech devices.

Once the devices were set up, the entire /24 subnet was scanned with RunZero starter edition. The raw results of this scan were put into a spreadsheet and then analyzed to remove uninvolved devices such as other computers and smartphones belonging to guests. In addition, other data not relevant (such as last-seen timestamps and detector-task info tied to the scanner) was stripped out for organization. This left a small file of targets consisting of the IoT devices and the directly tied infrastructure in use, but the resultant information wasn't quite complete due to RunZero being a free starter edition. This was resolved partially by logging into the wireless router and cross-referencing hostname, IP address, and MAC address information. This information was then manually added into the spreadsheet.

This spreadsheet then became a reference file for the simulated "attacker" node. To simulate scanning and poking for vulnerabilities, the Kali Linux VM was booted up into the graphical desktop and the Legion tool was called from the Kali menu. Legion was chosen because it provided a graphical tool that in turn allowed for a variety of Nmap scans to be run in a click-and-point as well as being able to import generated XML files. Legion also provided Nmap command syntax which could then be run in a raw Linux

terminal.

From there, each device was then scanned within Legion via staged Nmap and UnicornUDP in order to pick up any further OS, port, and service information available. Based on the received information, it was then possible to call up specialized Nmap scans depending on the service (for example, Nmap's library of specific HTTP/HTTPS enumeration and brute-forcing scripts).

While this was ongoing, two network scans were run on one physical computer that also contained a Windows 11 VM. Attached physically to the host and directed to the Windows VM was a Nordic nRF52840 dongle set with firmware geared for low-power RF sniffing. Windows was assigned the task of sniffing the network on an ongoing basis for low-rate wireless (IEEE 802.15.4) frames with the goal of seeing what was being transmitted, where the traffic originated, and where the traffic went. This was accomplished with Wireshark 4.0 and an added external interface tied to the dongle.

The other scan was configured with a standard install of Wireshark 4.0 on an older iMac running macOS Monterey. This iMac was used as it had both wired and wireless connections that enabled capturing both the wireless subnet as well as the underlying wired nodes consisting of a Juniper SRX300-series branch router/firewall and two older Ciena 3900-series optical switches.

Captures in PCAP-NG format were taken and analyzed to determine traffic flows and protocols being used. This included looking for both IPv4 and IPv6 traffic. If possible, further information was recorded regarding service versions and other notable

characteristics from a security standpoint.

To track down other devices, a pass was made using both an MQTT browser and the Flame Network Services application. This review showed that there were differing connections available, such as via HomeKit APIs that run over both TCP and UDP as well as IEEE 802.15.4 frames that communicate between devices (such as the IKEA Tradfri nodes that employ Zigbee) and with the configured “home bridge” on the local network.

Given all of this information on hardware and software versions, basic checks were run within OWASP-ZAP, the Legion tool within Kali Linux 2023.2, as well as the online copy of Exploit-DB. The purpose of these checks was to determine if any of the devices had obvious exploits, such as those readily usable with tools such as Metasploit. In addition, the tools looked at open ports, software versions, and related other information that in turn could be used to draw up a potential list of attacks against these devices.

If there were items found, these items would in turn serve as a starting point to design a method to attack and fully compromise the target system. If not, then such a finding would imply that more complicated and/or technically-skilled attacks would be necessary; a simple and unsophisticated attacker wouldn't be able to simply attack and compromise the device with typical “click-and-run” attacks. Worth noting is that such a finding wouldn't necessarily mean that the device isn't vulnerable; rather that the device's designs are currently sufficient to cover the most basic and obvious low-effort attacks.

After all, it is still entirely possible that a particularly skilled attacker could compromise these devices if given enough time and resources. However, the focus here is to look for obvious vulnerabilities that could be exploited by the unsophisticated if the device is

installed “out of the box.”

To see if any of the devices were prone to easy compromising by way of credentials, password-based attack attempts were made on the devices with THC-Hydra and a basic wordlist constructed with common passwords and default credentials. By attempting to directly compromise the devices with known weak and/or common default passwords, this performed a simple check to see if any of the devices out of the box were configured with such credentials.

3.2.2 Defining the Data

The data is being stored in different formats due to the variety of tools being used. It is not enough to simply condense every bit of data into a uniform package file, but rather the different formats are set to allow for effective organization of the collected data.

First, the packet captures previously discussed are being stored on the 5TB external drive attached to the iMac hosting the Windows VM. Both machines have read/write access to the drive thanks to using basic SMB-based sharing of the external disk as an effective network share. All of these packet captures were set up in Wireshark 4.0.x with the defaults selected aside from the 802.15.4 collector configured as an external capture per the manufacturer’s SDK instructions. While the IEEE 802.15.4 capture files aren’t large, the overall network captures are and thus were auto-split at 120MB increments to allow individual files to load within Wireshark without completely crashing either observing computer. The data collection scans total approximately 5 GB.

On the "attacking" computer, the Legion Tool (under the 01-Information Gathering menu on Kali Linux 2023.2) was used with standard Kali defaults as a means of running and organizing the results chiefly from Nmap scans. Legion is configured to stow its data into a file formatted for use with SQLite 3 and yet provide a simple integrated interface for accessing and acting on the information.

There was also spreadsheet carrying the data from RunZero that was used as a baseline map and set to be compatible with Microsoft Excel 365. By importing the RunZero into a standard XLSX, it becomes possible not just for file-sharing and conversion into various tables and other visualization and analysis efforts as they are needed, but also as a seamless way to export the data for repeatable analysis and use.

All of these pieces taken together formed the data used in the analysis as each piece had a specific role to play. The spreadsheet, as mentioned, carried raw data that was collected from RunZero and thus provided further information on IP addresses, potential operating systems, and potential services. The various packet captures were useful for understanding not only the raw traffic traversing the network, but also for specific data on protocols and streams resulting from the usage of these devices. Legion's SQLite3 database enabled storage of various additional Nmap queries and results that arose based on information gleaned from RunZero and other tools that were run. In addition to images and firmware used for the individual devices, the total amount of raw data generated was 5.28GB.

4 RESULTS

Once the network and all of the appropriate devices were set up, connections were tested and basic functionality (such as cameras being able to see things in its line-of-sight and the garage door functioning off of the wireless) was verified. This established the home and devices were set up as outlined in the previous chapter.

To start, each of the devices were scanned with Nmap on the wireless network. This information was triggered largely (but not fully) within the Legion tool running on Kali Linux 2023.2. This tool served as the a simple way of keeping the portscan data and findings relatively organized, as it also allowed the import of additional hosts and Nmap scans performed on the Kali box (or elsewhere, for that matter) so long as the Nmap command contained the `-oX` flag for XML output. The mechanism underlying this system is a flat file that opens into a SQLite3-compatible database. Accordingly, Legion is also able to hold artifacts captured with Nmap script output such as screenshots of running HTTP(S) services.

An example of the window that Legion uses is depicted below in figure 4.1:

From there, a good cross-section of the network and protocols were visible. By default, Legion was able to show whether the scanned device had open ports, and in many cases was able to make reasonably-close deductions on the service versions. Such information in turn can provide a wealth of insight for later when vulnerabilities and other potential attack points are investigated. Thus, it's worth noting the results of the initial port-scan as follows:

Figure 4.1: Example of Legion Window

Model	IP address	Open TCP Ports	Open UDP Ports
Archer A20	172.20.10.1	22, 53, 80, 443, 1900, 1990	53, 1900, 5351
Homey Bridge	172.20.10.22	None	None
Kasa Outdoor Plug	172.20.10.40	None	5353
32" Roku TV	172.20.10.48	7000, 8060, 37214, 42110, 51925, 52348, 56955, 57053, 57697	1900

Table 4.1 continued from previous page

RPi HomeBridge	172.20.10.67	22, 80, 443, 1883, 8088, 8581, 35017, 39881, 51532	5353
C253 myQ Door Opener	172.20.10.104	80, 443	None
Samsung 7 Series	172.20.10.128	8080	5353
HomePod Mini	172.20.10.152	53, 853, 5000, 7000, 7100, 49152, 49155, 57196, 62078	53, 5353
Circle View Camera	172.20.10.157	49152	5353
Eufy Security Camera	172.20.10.220	554, 55248	5353
Arlo Spotlight Camera	172.20.10.230	None	None
Nanoleaf A19 47FH	fd9c Unique-Local	None	5683
Nanoleaf A19 063S	fd9c Unique-Local	None	5683
Eve Energy Plug		None	None
Trådfri Outlet		None	None
Trådfri Switch		None	None
Wemo SmartPlug		None	None

Table 4.1: Portscan Results

This initial scan, coupled with quite a bit of guesswork on the part of Nmap's service-detection scripts, provided a lot of initial insight into what's been going on the

network. To start, it's clear that there's been a fair amount of network activity going on with multicast DNS (also known as Bonjour, avahi, and zeroconf), which makes logical sense given that IoT devices typically are sparse on resources, so basic network configuration via zeroconf would be more efficient than, say, managing a DHCP client and/or requiring input of manual addressing information.

Oddly enough, the Archer A20 router was found by Nmap's service detection to be running a version of Dropbear SSH that is vulnerable to CVE-2012-0920. However, it appears this particular exploit is something that as of this writing is not readily available for an unsophisticated attacker to use (for example, as a Metasploit module).

We can also gather that besides the router, there are a lot of open services floating around on the RPi HomeBridge device at 172.20.10.67 and some on the HomePod Mini at 172.20.10.152. These nodes provide potential opportunities to explore further and to see if devices could be compromised by taking out or compromising a major hub.

After the ports were scanned, the protocols themselves were investigated with Wireshark both for the traditional TCP/IP network as well as a sniffer for IEEE 802.15.4 frames. Both scans showed that there was plenty of interesting traffic and different protocols being used that account for what's going on. The following table illustrates the significant protocols that were seen in the captured Ethernet-frame traffic:

Protocols Observed	Port(s)	TCP/UDP	Purpose
Secure Shell	22	TCP	Remote Connections
DNS	53	TCP, UDP	Domain Name System

Table 4.2 continued from previous page

HTTP	80, 8080	TCP	HTTP Web Server
HTTP Secure	443	TCP	Secure HTTP
RTSP	554	TCP	Real-Time Streaming
MQTT	1883	TCP	Telemetry Transport
SSDP	1900	UDP	Simple Service Discovery Protocol
Apple AirPlay	5000, 7000, 7100	TCP	Apple Streaming
mDNS	5353	UDP	Multicast DNS / Zeroconf
CoAP	5683	UDP	IoT Communication
UPnP - TCP	8060	TCP	Roku Plug-and-Play

Table 4.2: Significant Observed Protocols - Ethernet

Noting these protocols, another targeted analysis was done within the collected scans. By taking 9 sample captures created by filtering out the scanning computers, an additional Mac, and the VM host and then combining them into a single PCAP enabled the analysis of traffic at key points with particular attention to look for distinct patterns in the traffic that could potentially give away or indicate IoT devices on the local network.

Given that these scans were run when there was the greatest likelihood of IoT activity, another picture began to emerge, namely that of key configuration protocols providing a significant share of the analyzed traffic:

IP Version	Layer 4 Transport	Protocol	Destination Port	Packet Count	Percentage
IPv4	UDP Datagram	UDP	8001, 15600, 25353	303732	49.686
IPv4	UDP Datagram	SSDP	1900	157055	25.692
IPv4	UDP Datagram	mDNS	5353	121615	19.894
IPv4	UDP Datagram	IGMP	N/A	27966	4.575
IPv4	UDP Datagram	DHCP	67	933	0.002

Table 4.3: Protocols Observed During Wireshark Analysis

We can even look at this further as a pie-chart:

Figure 4.2: Visualization of Protocols

What's interesting is that virtually all of the traffic here was carried as UDP datagrams across the network. Outside of the catch-all UDP traffic, the lion's share of the identified traffic was carried by SSDP and mDNS, two key protocols used in zero-configuration networking; and two protocols often used by IoT devices to exchange networking information.

On the 802.15.4 side, virtually all of the frames captured were Zigbee 3.0 traffic going between the two IKEA devices that are built to use Zigbee and the RPi's Zigbee2MQTT service. This traffic in turn enabled the devices to work and ultimately show up in the Apple HomeKit framework.

With the protocol analyses complete and considering the simulated skill of the attacker, four of the sixteen devices were then directly attacked. In order, attempts were made at compromising the devices with passwords, first over SSH, and then over HTTP and HTTPS. The wordlists entered for usernames and passwords used were built from a combination of installed Kali defaults and from a Github raw text file containing a list of common embedded usernames and passwords.

After this, an attempt was made with a compiled version of Cameradar to determine if any of the camera feeds would be detected and potentially prone to interception. The output of Cameradar is shown below in Figure 4.3.

Ultimately, the final results of what happened to the devices can be viewed here:

Model	IP address	Compromise	How?	Severity
Archer A20	172.20.10.1	No	N/A	N/A

Table 4.4 continued from previous page

Homey Bridge	172.20.10.22	No	N/A	N/A
Kasa Outdoor Plug	172.20.10.40	No	N/A	N/A
32" Roku TV	172.20.10.48	Partial	Abuse on port 8060	Nuisance
RPi HomeBridge	172.20.10.67	Full	Default Login: SSH	Critical
C253 myQ Door Opener	172.20.10.104	Partial	No Link to Pi, DoS	Nuisance
Samsung 7 Series	172.20.10.128	No	N/A	N/A
HomePod Mini	172.20.10.152	No	N/A	N/A
Circle View Camera	172.20.10.157	No	N/A	N/A
Eufy Security Camera	172.20.10.220	No	N/A	N/A
Arlo Spotlight Camera	172.20.10.230	Partial	DoS	Unusable
Nanoleaf A19 47FH	fd9c Unique-Local	No	N/A	N/A
Nanoleaf A19 063S	fd9c Unique-Local	No	N/A	N/A
Eve Energy Plug		No	N/A	N/A
Trådfri Outlet		Partial	No Link to Pi	Unusable
Trådfri Switch		Partial	No Link to Pi	Unusable
Wemo SmartPlug		No	N/A	N/A

Table 4.4: Results of Scans and Attacks

This shows that one device (the Raspberry Pi 4B running HomeBridge) was fully compromised, three more devices were rendered functionally unusable with respect to

```

(jrzeznik@kali)-[~]
└─$ cameradar -t 172.20.10.220 -p 554,5554,8554,55248
Loading credentials ... ok
Loading routes ... ok
Scanning the network ... ok
Attacking routes of 1 streams ... ok
Attempting to detect authentication methods of 1 streams ... ok
Attacking credentials of 1 streams ... ok
Validating that streams are accessible ... ok
Second round of attacks ... ok
Validating that streams are accessible ... ok
✘ Admin panel URL:      http://172.20.10.220/ You can use this URL to try attacking the camera's admin panel instead.
Available:              ✘
IP address:             172.20.10.220
RTSP port:              554
This camera does not require authentication
Username:
Password:
RTSP routes:
not found (known)

✘ Streams were found but none were accessed. They are most likely configured with secure credentials and routes. You can try adding entries to the dictionary or generating your own in order to attempt a bruteforce attack on the cameras.

```

Figure 4.3: Output of Cameradar, against the Eufy Camera

their intended functions, and two were partially hit with annoyance/nuisance tricks.

Of the devices that were examined, one was fully compromised and able to be exploited. This was the HomeBridge node running on the Raspberry Pi 4B. The underlying OS was compromised ultimately due to usage of default passwords. As a result, anyone could log into the device and, as it turns out, easily gain root-level access with the `sudo(1)` command.

With root access secured, setting a specific root password and enabling root access via SSH was trivial within the terminal. These actions allowed for persistence and the ability to download and build additional software onto the device such as current copies of Wireshark and Nmap.

```

(jrzeznik@kali)-[~]
└─$ sudo hydra -L usernames.txt -P Hydra2.txt -e nsr -t 16 172.20.10.67 ssh
sudo: unable to resolve host kali: Name or service not known
Hydra v9.5 (c) 2023 by van Hauser/THC & David Maciejak - Please do not use in military or secret service organizations, or for illegal purposes (this is non-binding, these *** ignore laws and ethics anyway).

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2023-06-28 08:42:06
[WARNING] Many SSH configurations limit the number of parallel tasks, it is recommended to reduce the tasks: use -t 4
[DATA] max 16 tasks per 1 server, overall 16 tasks, 9440 login tries (l:80/p:118), ~590 tries per task
[DATA] attacking ssh://172.20.10.67:22/
[STATUS] 158.00 tries/min, 158 tries in 00:01h, 9284 to do in 00:59h, 14 active
[STATUS] 136.67 tries/min, 410 tries in 00:03h, 9032 to do in 01:07h, 14 active
[STATUS] 130.00 tries/min, 910 tries in 00:07h, 8532 to do in 01:06h, 14 active
[STATUS] 123.27 tries/min, 1849 tries in 00:15h, 7594 to do in 01:02h, 13 active
[STATUS] 112.81 tries/min, 3497 tries in 00:31h, 5946 to do in 00:53h, 13 active
[STATUS] 106.34 tries/min, 4998 tries in 00:47h, 4445 to do in 00:42h, 13 active
[22][ssh] host: 172.20.10.67 login: pi password: raspberry
[STATUS] 104.24 tries/min, 6567 tries in 01:03h, 2876 to do in 00:28h, 13 active
^CThe session file ./hydra.restore was written. Type "hydra -R" to resume session.

(jrzeznik@kali)-[~]
└─$ █

```

Figure 4.4: Output of THC-Hydra against HomeBridge

By compromising the HomeBridge, this effectively compromised control of the garage door opener and both IKEA Zigbee accessories. All three of these devices were integrated into the HomeKit-based mainstem by way of HomeBridge. Thus, being able to perform functions, run automations, or otherwise get details from these devices via the Apple HomeKit frameworks failed precisely because all of these devices were no longer connected to HomeKit.

Other devices impacted were the garage door opener and the Arlo camera. Both were taken down by way of DoS attacks, but in different ways. The Arlo camera lost connectivity intermittently during the Nmap scans, and rendered the feed as jumpy within the connected iPhone app. On the other hand, the Chamberlain myQ garage door was mostly further cut off by DoS via Hping3 against its open webserver ports. Both devices were not accessed internally, but instead were effectively knocked offline though some of

their functions that weren't necessarily related to network-based control continued to function (like the spotlight on the camera and the RF-based remotes for the garage door).

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Unpacking What Happened

The results in the last chapter in and of themselves alone provide a wealth of insight, not all of which is clear at first glance. There are patterns, clues, and other small pointers that emerge when the entire scenario and its data are laid out. Even so, there is enough there to consider what might have made the most impact. Indeed, there was one single item that proved to be the most surprising.

It is worth remembering that the lab environment had sixteen devices, configured to defaults without the apparent benefit of additional security hardening or other practices that were not prompted for as part of the out-of-the-box setup. Thus, devices were configured as they were, so if there were hard-coded or default credentials set, those were being used. This was also true of any protocol configuration (for example, if the setup didn't provide an option to turn off insecure versions such as HTTP on port 80 or CoAP on port 5683).

Despite this out-of-the-box configuration, most of the actual IoT devices themselves didn't appear to have any obvious footholds that would make it trivial for an unsophisticated attacker to get in and cause too much damage. It is vital to recognize that this does not *ipso facto* imply that the devices are secure against all, or even most, attacks. In all likelihood, there probably are serious security issues around these devices floating around, and skilled attackers can no doubt sniff around, detect, and exploit these vulnerabilities.

However, the built-up HomeBridge controller was easily compromised with default credentials over the SSH protocol. This as it turns out is not so much the fault of the

HomeBridge software, but rather a quirk that comes with Raspbian, the Debian-based Linux distro designed for the Raspberry Pi line. Raspbian by default enables SSH open on port 22 and has the default credentials set as *pi:raspberry*. The general assumption is that most people installing Raspbian are familiar enough with Linux and Linux security to change the password.

In all fairness to the Raspbian team, this isn't an unreasonable assumption given the Raspberry Pi's reputation as something geared for the more technically-inclined. Indeed, the default "message of the day" shown when logging in emphasizes the necessity of changing the default password and/or setting up a separate user on the machine. Despite this configuration and the well-meaning assumption, and because these devices are available to the general public regardless of technical skill, the usage of default credentials still presents a large hole that can be easily exploited.

The effects of the compromise were also visible beyond the Raspberry Pi. Once the Pi was compromised and effectively taken offline, three more devices that were reliant on it and the installed HomeBridge software to connect into the HomeKit architecture were also made unavailable: the Chamberlain myQ garage door opener and two IKEA Trådfri devices (a switch and a smart plug that used ZigBee2MQTT to filter into HomeKit).

What this all means is that the compromise wasn't so much focused on the individual IoT devices themselves but instead on the controllers, data-in-motion, and protocols. It was far easier to go after a weaker controller that in turn supervised several devices instead of directly going after an individual device or sensor.

The other two devices that were hit with attacks were ones that also happened to be directly connected to the wireless network and brought down with denial-of-service (DoS) attacks. These are fairly simple to pull off, but as the results showed, resulted in more of a nuisance than an actual failure of the system. These systems remained intact in that the attacker wasn't able to get into the firmware, change settings or manipulate the data processing functions on the device; instead they were only able to sniff the traffic and disrupt the flow in a way that rendered the devices temporarily unusable for their intended purpose.

For example, the opener was still able to lift the garage door if the wired button in the garage (or the RF remote in the car) was pressed and there was also the option of manually disconnecting the opener assembly from the door. As a result, it was still possible to enter and exit the house through the garage door, but just not as convenient. This essentially rendered the myQ-enabled opener as just another traditional garage-door opener with nothing fancy about it.

Likewise, the Arlo camera was simply knocked offline for a bit while being scanned or pinged but came back after the attacking stopped. While this did have an impact on the usability of the camera, the placement and function revealed that this was a nuisance as it was set on a balcony to watch for birds. In addition, the spotlight still worked if it was turned on, but just couldn't be shut off. This again would be placed as more of a nuisance and not a full-on compromise of the device in the same way that a random outage caused naturally (for example, a nearby thunderstorm) could temporarily cause service issues on outdoor devices.

5.2 If All of That Happened, What's Next?

5.2.1 So How Does This Apply to the Hospital Room?

If we consider what a modern American hospital room looks like, we know that in addition to the usual physical layout (such as a bathroom, visitor furniture, and the closet), there are also connected devices that may be capable of smart connections. These would include the bed, the TV, and perhaps even the room's thermostat. Finally, there are the actual medical devices themselves that might be used in the patient's care. As an example, consider the below figure from Hudson and Hempel (2022):

Figure 5.1: Hempel's Connected Hospital Room

The days of a simple bed-and-TV are long past. Today's hospital room has the capability of remote sensors, paging, diagnosis, and treatment. These in-room devices leverage low-power and real-time technologies to provide consistent and accurate monitoring of the patient and in doing so are using protocols, hardware, and processes developed as part of the IoT world.

Thus, it is worth noting that IoT devices across various uses have similar profiles, builds, and uses. Those on a traditional TCP/IP network all use protocols and ports that can be scanned and interacted with Wireshark, Nmap, netcat, and a host of other tools available. Even still, not all devices make use of traditional TCP/IP stacks and use technologies such as Bluetooth Low-Energy (BLE), CoAP, and 6LoWPAN that don't tend to show up on most regularly-configured network scans.

What this ultimately means is that IoT devices, regardless of where they are used or their purpose, share far more similarities than most people think. Considering that many, if not most, IoT devices are designed around a System on a Chip (SoC) design to leverage low-power architecture capabilities (for example, those found in lower-cost ARM and MIPS chips).

As was mentioned in the introduction chapter, there are an average of 15-20 connected devices in an average hospital room and the majority are most likely end-of-life with older technology. Most are sensors that collect and send data onward to a more centralized collection point or application for processing. Naturally, these devices are going to be producing and passing on traffic, most likely over RF media such as Wi-Fi or Bluetooth radios, or through a specific customized protocol such as through Nmap.

Thus, It's entirely plausible to think that these devices are dripping with vulnerabilities that would make them attractive targets for attack even considering the transient nature of hospital rooms. Scanning those devices for old services, protocol aberrations, and/or default credentials for access are largely going to be the same process-wise. The key difference is that a well-equipped SecOps team may have newer or more complete tools that can largely automate the process into the network background and generate key reports for management with only a few clicks.

As the Illinois hospital case mentioned earlier shows, cyber-attacks against hospitals and healthcare systems aren't going away, and neither are the issues regarding older devices currently in use. Absent a major order through regulation, these devices are going to remain in use until they are worn down and forced to be replaced. With a majority of devices being past the end of life, it is conceivable that every practice and every system using these devices are open to attack at any time without the benefits of vendor support or updates. This alone makes finding these devices, documenting them, and applying appropriate compensating controls all the more critical.

What might that look like? If a hospital is said to never close and is always open to the public, anyone could walk in and try to poke around while a relative or someone else is receiving care. These days, it's not suspicious to have a laptop on a hospital visit, and this laptop could be scanning around – but is the network in turn scanning and looking for these actors? Are they segregated off to their own guest network? Up-to-date network would easily answer these questions.

In addition, does the SecOps team at this given hospital do regular audits of devices? Surely at some point, devices aren't being used for patient care and somebody could go

and periodically check to see if these devices have open ports or open communications that could easily be sniffed out with Wireshark. Those systems with more resources may even be able to find sensors that could detect this and feed back into their Security Orchestration and Response (SOAR) systems.

System IT staff should be aware that because IoT and IoMT are often lower-power devices, using a packet scanner on the configured TCP/IP network may not be enough. Scanning with a 802.15.4 sniffer could also detect IoT protocols such as Zigbee and 6LoWPAN that might be transmitting, and having an mDNS application could look to see if devices are putting out their info on UDP port 5353. These are simple things that can be done even in a small system with limited resources; Wireshark is free and a reliable dongle for IEEE 802.15.4 sniffing from Nordic Semi runs about \$20 online. Taking advantage of these tools could at some point translate into a life-saving operation.

5.2.2 Conclusions

From a purely-practical standpoint, it does appear that newer devices on the market are taking some measures of security seriously. For example, most of the devices covered weren't easily affected, and even for the few that were, the vast majority created temporary nuisances versus genuine security headaches.

Importantly, this finding should **not** be considered as a clean bill of health. Rather, this is to say that there were no blatantly-obvious flaws that could be exploited by just about anybody with a laptop and some Google searching. Nor is it meant to be a periodic "run and forget" test to check a box on a to-do list. Instead, what this experiment shows is that IoT devices in general have more similarities than people think, and that securing them is an ongoing process. While newer devices often do have some considerations built into

their design, they are still far from being the type of devices that could truly afford to be "set and forgotten."

This of course raises a pertinent question: what about older devices still sitting on the network? The answer would be quite simple if we start by looking for the obvious holes such as insecure protocols, configuration errors, spurious traffic, and default credentials. Knowing where these weak points are is half the battle, as it is far easier to construct appropriate compensating security controls when the weak points are already known and documented.

On this same point, the sheer importance of current documentation in enterprise or other mission-critical environments cannot be emphasized enough. Without a way to know what is currently meant to be on the network, it becomes extremely difficult to discern genuine devices and activity as part of the enterprise versus rogue actors.

Likewise, what if the IT staff were able to go into an empty hospital room and sniff out the protocols and traffic coming from the devices within? What would that yield?

Unfortunately, this is something that has been rather hard to do. Not only is it hard to predict having a spare room available, but also the prospect of inadvertently listening in and picking up protected health data. Consequently, this has yet to be done, but would present an excellent opportunity for research going forward.

As these devices age and/or newer and more medically-effective devices are developed, the question of replacement is always raised. What if hospital systems or the government insisted on continuing security support as an inextricable part of the evaluation for medical efficacy? It's a question that's definitely worth asking, and again another

completely valid path for research both academically and within the industry itself.

Even with these promising points, the status quo of poor documentation and limited availability for security auditing is unfortunately a common state of affairs based on the author's own experience as an information security engineer for an interstate health system located in the Midwestern U.S. All too often, there aren't accurate figures as to what the devices are and where they are at. This is to say nothing of tracking potential vulnerabilities and being able to follow up on the appropriate support contracts when a major hole is found.

5.2.3 Recommendations

First and foremost, the whole concept of home-based IoT devices needs to be thought out and reimaged, especially if the goal is to encourage widescale public adoption. While taking care of basic items like setting strong passwords and keeping the systems up-to-date may seem like common-sense things, earlier studies have shown that people tend to "set and forget." Thus, the key to stronger home security must necessarily lie in design for the simple reason that vendors can no longer assume that their customers are going to be able to perform hardening outside of wizard apps or plain-language walkthroughs in the initial documentation.

HomeBridge itself actually has valid 2FA account support (such as with Google Authenticator or Cisco Duo), which works fine as long as a solid time source (such as a reliable connection to an Internet time server) is available. This is something that might want to be turned on with clear and simple instructions on how to properly configure, especially with the increasing ubiquity of 2FA/MFA apps being used elsewhere.

Raspbian ships with default credentials and SSH exposed. This is normally not a good idea even if the basic assumption is that users who are buying RPi nodes are somewhat technically-savvy and should naturally know better. After all, not everyone who buys a Raspberry Pi and follows directions they see on a website is necessarily aware of the need to either change the default credentials or disable the service altogether. It may make sense for those apps that also build OS images off of standard Raspbian (like the HomeBridge) image used in the lab to disable SSH unless it's absolutely necessary or to force a change in username and password.

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